

Artistic the work to the winter preparation

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The work to the winter from entering before students artistic the work to study preparation must will be Because students work content right perception reach for life about known to the imagination have to be necessary Of this for preparation works will be held . As you know , in the classroom reading based on artistic and popular science texts stands Read the students text with introduction to study preparation from the stage starts . Preparation stage writers about information give , students in the work to be described events perception make , work to feel the pathos , stranger and a lot meaningful words are more complicated kind of figurative expressions explain such as issues own into takes If the work year seasons about if so , nature to his bosom travel organization is also in the classroom reading success to provide service does

Text with initial from dating after as follows questions with appeal to do in class of students activity increases :

1. In the story which the episode Do you think it's interesting ?

2. Story of the heroes which one's behavior do you approve Which one's character , self catch to you didn't like it ?

3. In life so people have you met

Preparation of work duties the following :

1. Students in the work reflection delivered events about imaginations enrichment , text conscious perception to do effect which new data to give , artistic in the work described the evidence of students own in his life observed with connect to receive conditions Create .

2. Writer's life and to his creation interest waking up For example , Zafar Diyar in the 4th grade life and creativity about as follows data to give possible : Zafar Diyar of Namangan region Quiet in the district was born Parents farmer was They are they lived in poverty . Zafar Diyar four to age when full his family To Tashkent moved will come . Mother in the printing house works of the poet himself while old at school reads Later on 7th children in Tashkent at home is brought up . of the poet the first poems set at the age of 21 clicked comes out

3. Read students the work emotional perception to do preparation

4. The work content to understand halal giving of words dictionary meanings explanation For example , 4th grade " Study winter " Map " text in the book on when working word and expressions dictionary as follows to be can :

Mouth zing opened be surprised being stay

From the mold came out like a brick - everyone side the same flat

Apathetic - indifferent

Discovery - research as a result created thing invention

Like a family sank - hard touched , hurt

In Pisa to do - in advance something a must to put to emphasize

Preparation of work educational forms different become a teacher work content and to the circumstances looking the work type chooses Preparation during what are about information to give the goal done if so , first of all , of the students from themselves they are about what they know asking is determined .

For example , " To the book " Ikhlos " work to the winter in preparation of students initial knowledge as follows defined as :

Teacher : - Today is our **Motherland** to the past travel we do Our journey Bukhara to the city will be Travelers two to the group is divided . Bukhara gates opening for one how many spells our solution necessary Of this for each one group to himself given questions done , to the podium rise necessary

For group 1 questions :

1. In history lived great from scientists , poets , writers , and generals who do you know

2. In Bukhara which great persons lived ?

3. In Bukhara historical buildings , places name tell me Same for group 2 kind of questions is given or each ikala group for that's it questions given , "Who first to the podium reached will go ?" condition it is put . To Khattakhta great persons portrait , historical places described pictures hanging it is put . Preparation from the forms one is an excursion . This is work from the type nature to the image dedicated or work output , construction , city , village to life , profession circle topics and historical works when studied use can For example , " In the Greenhouse " in the 1st grade , " Metropolitan " in the 2nd grade topics from learning before excursion to do to the goal according to Excursion of students in the work expression done events clearly and conscious to their mastery help gives knowledge deepens , nature events observation and them clearly describe skills forms . Excursion in children to nature love wakes him up to love and nature donations save feeling educates . Work release enterprises , museum and another to places excursions while historical of events

right perception that they can provides adults work with introduces the reader to work love wakes up , to the profession directs .

Film screening to do Historical materials , work the author his life from learning before the movie screening if done , the students the work perception to do activates . For example , the story " Gulzorda " in the 2nd grade read in the winter " from Mehrob from the movie " Scorpion " . fragment showing about Ibn Sina in the 3rd-4th grades works in learning " Ulugbek treasure " , Alisher Navoi about works with in the introduction " Alisher " Navoi " movie screening to be done can

Movie and from slides the students the work to study preparation during is used . They are of students imagination to do , their understanding to clarify , conscious reading and emotional perception to reach help will give . At the students ' film screening born some to the questions their themselves new student from the works answer they find Preparation their work such organize of students to study has been also increases their interests . He is a teacher the story This is the method work the author about information in giving the most efficient is considered The work the author a poet and writers about in words while being given their portraits , children for wrote works demonstration if possible , of students the author to his creativity interests increases . Get started in class poet , writers own from the language studied works or they are about others said thoughts magnet from the tape if broadcast or from a video feed shown to him teacher story if it joins , teach it efficiency more increases . For example , Uzbekistan in the 4th grade Republic State Mathias after being told , A. Oripov's himself " Uzbekistan " poem by put broadcast can He is a teacher the writer and poets about information students level suitable It 's exciting by doing story students artistic the work to study internal desire increases in them book to study love increases . Writer about information from 1st grade to 4th grade when you go until raised and deepened will go Read the students independent to search to teach again one method to the students in advance the writer or work written period about books , resources recommendation from them data collection , albums preparation , then students themselves determined information read and speak is to give From class to class move with the writer life and creativity about students knowledge increased goes The work the author with to introduce placed requirements will also increase . He is a teacher short information from giving the writer life with more complete to introduce passes . In this he is small school age of students to his age suitable opportunities , they the writer with where level familiar the fact that and his from his works what that he has read account takes